

UGC Approved, Journal No. 48416 (IJCR), Impact Factor 6.0

ISSN : 2393-8358

Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research
An International Peer Reviewed Refereed Research Journal

Vol. 10, No. 11

November, 2023

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Published by

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